

FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF ORAL DISINTEGRATING TABLETS OF DESLORATADINE

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ABSTRACT:

Orally disintegrating Tablets (ODTs) are an impressive dosage form that breaks down in the mouth upon contact with saliva; thus, they do not require any additional water and disintegrate within seconds, providing a quick onset of action and maximum convenience for oral administration. Patient adherence may be a challenge for bitter medications, as the unpleasant taste could deter usage unless it is adequately masked. Desloratadine is a second-generation tricyclic antihistamine that acts selectively as a peripheral H₁-antagonist. The current study attempted to create oral disintegrating Desloratadine tablets using the Direct compression method. Superdisintegrants such as SSG and Croscopolvidone alone or in combination were used to create a total of nine batches of ODT containing desloratadine. Sweeteners such as Betadex, Mannitol, and sucralose were used to cover up the harsh taste of the medication. All of the created formulations were found to be within standard limits, according to the preformulation experiments. Every formulation that was created was also put through a number of ODT quality control tests, and the outcomes showed that they were all within acceptable bounds. All of the developed materials had a disintegration time of 30 seconds.

The drug release studies were conducted up to 5min for all the developed formulations and among all the formulations F9 was found to be the best formulations as higher amount i.e., 99.45 % of drug was released within 5 minutes. So, we had successfully developed Desloratadine ODT.

Keywords: Oral disintegrating tablets, Direct compression

Introduction:

Desloratadine is a second-generation, tricyclic antihistamine which has a selective and peripheral H₁-antagonist action. It is an effective descarboethoxy metabolite of loratadine (a second-generation histamine). Receptor-binding data specify that at a concentration of 2-3 mg/mL (7 nanomolar), desloratadine indicates significant interaction with the human histamine H₁ receptor.¹ Desloratadine have a long-lasting effect and do not cause drowsiness because they do not readily enter into the central nervous system. Desloratadine belongs to the class of organic compounds known as benzocyclo-hepta-pyridines. These are aromatic compounds comprising a benzene ring and a pyridine ring fused to a 7-membered carbocycle. In general, many physical and chemical factors can have a negative effect on the stability of carbonic inhibitor.²

Oral administration is the most widely used and convenient route with high stability and a small packaging size^{3,4}. The orally disintegrating tablet (ODT), as a delivery system, rapidly disintegrates in the mouth upon contact with saliva; therefore, it does not need additional water. It is available for absorption through pregastric mucosa. Mouth dissolving/disintegrating tablets (MDTs), quick disintegrating tablets, fast/rapid dissolving or disintegrating tablets (FDTs), quick/rapid melt tablets, orodispersible tablets, and porous tablets are the other recorded names for this type of dosage form^{5,6}. The need for rapid disintegration, rapid onset of action, and patient compliance, especially for paediatric, geriatric, psychiatric, paralyzed, and bedridden patients, leads to the emergence of OTDs in the 1980s⁷.

Material & methods:

Desloratadine was obtained from Glochem Industries limited, Sodium starch glycolate from Gujarat micro wax private limited, Crospovidone from Saraf Resins & Chemicals Private Limited. All other chemicals used were of laboratory grade.

Preformulation Studies:^[27]

Preformulation studies are conducted to characterize the API and excipients physical and chemical properties for designing of the dosage form. In which the investigation of physical and chemical properties of drug alone and combined with excipients.

API characterization:

- A. Colour of the drug sample:** The drug samples was viewed visually for the determination of its colour using white and dark background and then the results were compared with official books and pharmacopoeias.
- B. Odour and taste of the drug sample:** The odour and taste of the drug sample results were compared with the official books and pharmacopoeias.
- C. Solubility:** Solubility of the API was determined by dissolving in water and organic solvents and then the results are compared with standards.
- D. Melting point:** The melting point of the pure API was determined by open capillary method. The capillary tube was closed at one end by fusion and was filled with the API by repeating tapings.

E. Preparation of standard stock solution:

The standard stock solution of Desloratidine is prepared by following method Dissolve 10 mg of Desloratidine drug in 10 ml of purified water to get 1 mg per 1 ml. Transfer 1 ml of standard stock solution to 100 ml volumetric flask and make up with purified water to get 10 µ/ml. The remaining dilutions from 5-35 µ/ml were prepared by above method; absorption maxima were determined for above standard samples. The spectra and absorbance of the solutions was measured against reagent blank by determination of UV absorption maxima at 231 nm and the calibration curve was plotted.

Drug-excipients compatibility studies: ^[28]

This study generally includes Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and these are generally performed to confirm the drug-excipients compatibility. To find compatibility between pure drugs with the excipients used in formulation, FTIR spectra of physical mixture of pure drugs and excipients were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer (Bruker) in scanning range of 4000–600/cm and the resolution was 1/cm. FTIR scans were then evaluated for shifting and masking and appearance of new peaks due to drug-excipients incompatibility. ^[2]

Accelerated stability studies:

Accelerated stability studies were performed out on formulated ODTs (Formulated in three primary batches) which were wrapped in aluminium foil and then stored in air-tight containers that are impermeable to solid, liquid, and gases, for 1 month as prescribed by ICH guidelines at temperature of 40°C ± 2°C and at ambient humidity

as well as at room temperature. The tablets were withdrawn on 15th and 30th day and analysed for drug content, friability, hardness, and *in-vitro* DT.

4.6.1 Pre-compression parameters:

1. Angle of repose (θ):^[28]

Angle of repose is defined as the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of the powder and horizontal plane. The frictional force in a loose powder or granules can be measured by angle of repose. It is an indicative of the flow properties of the powder.

$$\tan \theta = H / R$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} (H/R)$$

Where, θ is the angle of repose

H is height of pile

R is radius of the base of pile

The powder mixture was allowed to flow through the funnel fixed to a stand at definite height (H). The angle of repose was then calculated by measuring the height & radius of the heap of powder formed. Care was taken to see that the powder particles slip & roll over each other through the sides of the funnel. Relationship between angle of repose and powder flow property.

2. Bulk density:^[29, 32]

The bulk density was obtained by dividing the mass of a powder by the bulk volume in cm³. The sample of about 50 cm³ of powder, previously been passed through a standard sieve no. 20, was carefully introduced into a 100 ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was dropped at 2-second intervals onto a hard wood surface three times from a height of 1 inch. The bulk density of each formulation was then obtained by dividing the weight of sample in grams by the final volume in cm³ of the sample contained in the cylinder. It was calculated by using equation below:

$$D_f = M/V_p$$

Where

D_f = Bulk density

M = Weight of samples in grams

V_p = Final volumes of granules in cm³

3. Tapped density:^[33]

The tapped density was obtained by dividing the mass of a powder by the tapped volume in cm³. The sample of about 50 cm³ of powder previously been passed

through a standard sieve no. 20, is carefully introduced into a 100 ml graduated cylinder. The cylinder was dropped at 2-second intervals onto a hard wood surface 100 times from a height of 1 inch. The tapped density of each formulation was then obtained by dividing the weight of sample in grams by the final tapped volume in cm^3 of the sample contained in the cylinder. It was calculated by using equation given below:

$$D_o = M/V_p$$

Where

D_o = Bulk density

M = Weight of samples in grams

V_p = Final volume of granules in cm^3

4. Carr's Index: ^[33]

An indirect method of measuring powder flow from bulk densities was developed by Carr. The percentage compressibility of a powder was a direct measure of the potential powder arch or bridge strength and stability. Carr's index of each formulation was calculated according to equation:

$$I = [(V_t - V_b) / V_t] \times 100$$

Where

V_t = Tapped density

V_b = Bulk density

5. Hausner's ratio: ^[33]

Hausner's ratio is the ratio of tapped density to the bulk density of the powder and it is an indirect of ease of powder flow.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \rho_t / \rho_d$$

Where

ρ_t = Tapped density

ρ_d = Bulk density

Formulation of Desloratadine ODT

Name of ingredient	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9
Desloratadine	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
Micro crystalline cellulose	38	37.96	37.46	38.46	37.96	37.46	35.46	34.46	33.46
Sodium starch glycolate	3	3.5	4				3	3.5	4
Crospovidone				3	3.5	4	3	3.5	4
Hydroxypropyl cellulose	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2

Betadex	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Sodium hydrogen carbonate	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Mannitol	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Citric acid anhydrous	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
Sucralose	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54	1.54
Magnesium stearate	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

4.5 MANUFACTURING PROCEDURE:

Fast dissolving tablets of Desloratidine were prepared by direct compression method. All the ingredients (except granular directly compressible excipients) were passed through # 60-mesh separately. The ingredients were then weighed and mixed in geometrical order and compressed into tablets of 125 mg using 6 mm round concave punches on an 8-station rotary tablet machine. All the prepared batches prepared were properly stored in a suitable container until it is used for further evaluation studies.

4.6 EVALUATION OF FORMULATION: ^[31]

4.6.2 POST COMPRESSION PARAMETERS:

1. Weight variation: ^[31]

Weight variation was determined to know whether different batches of tablets have uniformity. Weighed 20 tablets individually, calculated the average weight and compared the individual tablet weights to the average. The tablets meet the test if not more than two tablets are outside the % limit and none of the tablet differ by more than two times the % limit.

2. Tablet Hardness: ^[31, 32]

The resistance of tablets to shipping or breakage under conditions of storage, transportation and handling before usage depends on its hardness. The hardness of tablet of each formulation was measured by Monsanto Hardness Tester. The hardness was measured in items of kg/cm^2 . Hardness or tablet crushing strength is the force required to break a tablet in a diametric compression. The force is measured in kg and the hardness of about $3\text{-}5 \text{ kg}/\text{cm}^2$ is considered to be satisfactory for uncoated tablets.

3. Friability (F): ^[28]

Friability of the tablet determined using Roche friabilator. This device subjects the tablet to the combined effect of abrasion and shock in a plastic chamber revolving at 25 rpm and dropping a tablet at a height of 6 inches in each revolution. Pre weighted sample of tablets was placed in the friabilator and were subjected to the 100 revolutions. Tablets were

dusted using a soft muslin cloth and reweighed. USP limit is 0.5 to 1%. The friability (F) is given by the formula

$$\text{Friability} = [1 - W_o / W] \times 100$$

Where

W_o = weight of tablet before test

W = weight of tablet after test

4. **Uniformity of Content:** ^[34,35]

10 tablets were selected randomly. Each tablet was transferred into a 50mL volumetric flask, dissolved and diluted to 50 mL with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. One ml of this solution was diluted to 100 ml with phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The amount of drug present in each tablet was determined by UV spectroscopy at 246 nm. Standard limit for uniformity of content is

IP: - Active less than 10mg or 10%, BP:- Active less than 2 mg or 2%, USP:- Active less than 25mg or 25%.

- 10 tabs limit NMT 1 tab deviate 85 – 115% & none outside 75 – 125% of the Average value/IP/BP/USP (Relative Standard Deviation less than or equal to 6%),
- If 2 or 3 individual values are outside the limits 85 – 115% of the Average value, & none outside 75 – 125% repeat for 20 tablets.

5. **Water absorption capacity:** ^[33]

The water absorption capacity provides an indirect assessment of the durability of a cementitious product, the tablet was weighed and place on a tissue paper and place in petri dish with water and then the tablet absorbs water and weighed calculate by using the formula

$$R = 100 \times W_b / W_a$$

Where

W_b = Weight of tablet before water absorption

W_a = Weight of tablet after water absorption

6. **In-vitro disintegration time:** ^[36, 37, 38]

The process of breakdown of a tablet into smaller particles is called as disintegration. The in-vitro disintegration time of a tablet was determined using disintegration test apparatus as per I.P. specifications.

I.P. Specifications: Place one tablet in each of the 6 tubes of the basket. Add a disc to each tube and run the apparatus using phosphate buffer (pH-6.8) maintained at $37^{\circ}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$ as the immersion liquid. The assembly should be raised and lowered between 30 cycles per minute in the phosphate buffer (pH-6.8) maintained at $37^{\circ}\pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$. The time in seconds taken for complete disintegration of the tablet with no palpable mass remaining in the apparatus was measured and recorded. Standard limit for disintegration time is within 3 min in water at $25^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 10\text{C}$ (IP) and $15 - 25^{\circ}\text{C}$ (BP).

9. Dissolution Studies: [28]

The release rate of Desloratidine from mouth dissolving tablets was determined using USP Dissolution Testing Apparatus II (Paddle type). The dissolution medium used was 900 ml of phosphate buffer pH 6.8 which was maintained at $37\pm 0.50\text{C}$. The paddle speed was kept at 50 rpm throughout the study. Five ml of samples was withdrawn at every 5 minutes interval and diluted to 10ml then 5ml of fresh dissolution media maintained at the same temperature was replaniced. The samples were analysed spectrophotometrically at 246nm using phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as blank. The raw dissolution data was analysed for calculating the amount of drug released upto 5 minutes. [39, 40]

Results and discussion:

5.1 EVALUATION OF PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES:

API Characterization:

Description:

Desloratadine is physically examined for appearance and colour.

Name of the parameter	Observation
Color	White
Odour	Characteristic
Taste	Bitter

Solubility:

Table No 5.1 Solubility of Desloratadine

S.No	Solvents used	Solubility parameter
1.	Water	Slightly soluble
2.	Ethanol	Soluble
3.	DMSO	Soluble

pH:

The pH of pure drug was determined using Digital pH meter

Table No 5.2 Melting & pH of Desloratidine

S. No	Melting point	pH
1.	157 ^o C	4.5

Construction of standard calibration curve:

Table No 5.4 Standard calibration curve of Desloratidine

Concentration ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Absorbance (nm)
0	0
5	0.118
10	0.254
15	0.369
20	0.528
25	0.680
30	0.798
35	0.889

Figure No 5.1 Standard calibration curve of Desloratidine

Drug-excipients compatibility studies:

Drug excipients compatibility studies were performed by FTIR studies

Fig No: FTIR Graph of Desloratidine and Cross povidone

5.2.1 Evaluation of pre compression parameters:

The evaluation of the powdered blend of the formulation are shown

Table No: 5.6 Pre compression parameters of Desloratadine blend

F.Code	Bulk density	Tapped density	Compressibility index	Hausner's ratio	Angle of repose
F1.	0.385	0.457	15.75	1.180	29.72
F2	0.372	0.441	15.64	1.185	29.03
F3	0.380	0.440	14.54	1.157	28.36
F4	0.388	0.454	14.53	1.170	30.70
F5	0.373	0.438	14.84	1.174	28.36
F6	0.387	0.451	14.19	1.165	29.37
F7	0.373	0.438	14.84	1.174	28.36
F8	0.381	0.440	14.91	1.171	29.32
F9	0.374	0.430	15.01	1.181	29.12

5.2.2 Evaluation of post compression parameters:

The evaluation of the post compression parameters of the tablets are shown below

Table No: 5.7 Post compression parameters of Desloratadine ODT

F.Code	Weight variation (mg)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Uniformity of content (%)	Water absorption (%)	Disintegration time (sec)
F1.	125.8 ± 2.4	2.8	0.416	88.68 ± 0.14	88.91 ± 0.96	26
F2.	124.2 ± 2.1	2.7	0.408	90.48 ± 0.13	90.48 ± 0.59	29
F3.	123.9 ± 2.8	2.8	0.502	93.62 ± 0.23	92.58 ± 0.45	27
F4.	126.2 ± 3.2	2.5	0.584	95.23 ± 0.06	91.98 ± 0.49	26
F5.	125.3 ± 2.2	2.9	0.516	95.57 ± 0.01	93.32 ± 0.48	28
F6.	124.8 ± 2.5	2.8	0.514	96.82 ± 0.02	95.25 ± 0.75	26
F7.	125.1 ± 1.5	2.5	0.572	98.69 ± 0.04	96.42 ± 0.82	25
F8	124.2± 1.5	2.4	0.571	97.25± 0.01	97.30± 0.81	24
F9	125.1 ± 1.5	2.5	0.573	98.12± 0.03	95.35± 0.83	24

5.2.3 IN VITRO DISSOLUTION STUDIES:**Table No: 5.8 In-Vitro dissolution drug release**

F. Code	% Drug released after 5 Min
F1	89.23±0.21
F2	91.57±0.41
F3	88.09±0.30
F4	91.14±0.28
F5	89.15±0.35
F6	88.66±0.41
F7	98.57±0.45
F8	99.01±0.51
F9	99.45±0.50

Conclusion:

In this current research work we had successfully formulated Desloratadine oral disintegrating tablet by Direct compression method using super disintegrating agents like sodium starch glycolate and cross povidone. All the formulations prepared were tested for all quality control tests of the tablets and the results obtained were found to be within specified limits of IP. *In-vitro* drug release studies shown that among all the developed formulations the F9 was the best formulation as the percentage drug release was found to be 99.45% within five minutes. So developed formulations had potential benefits like improved patient compliance by masking bitter taste of the Desloratadine, rapid on set of action and ease of administration.

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